

Cultural Vocabulary of Chinese Novel in “Three Lives Three Worlds, Ten Miles of Peach Blossoms”

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This research aims to compare and classify cultural vocabulary. Including studying the Chinese language and culture from the cultural vocabulary by comparing from the novel “Three Lives Three Worlds, Ten Miles of Peach Blossoms”, The Chinese version by TangQiGongZi and The Thai version by Suree Pruksanusak. It will be based on Peter Newmark's theory of language and culture help for comparison and analysis. Because in the process of translation, The big problem that translators have to face Is the interpretation of a word or language that must be linked to the culture of the other country, Peter Newmark discovered five cultural vocabulary that will connect language and culture together. To reduce the translation barriers, In terms of environmental culture, objects culture, social culture, language cultural, gestures and habits cultural.

The research results found that the culture vocabulary has 298, the most discovered cultural vocabulary is related to language has 128 (42.96%), followed by cultural vocabulary related to society has 103 (34.56%), objects has 39 (13.09%), environment has 24 (8.05%), gestures and habits have 4 (1.35%). The language cultural words found are the use of family pronoun, calling myself, calling other people and names of positions. It shows that Chinese society is a society that adheres to the senior system, class division, respect and humility to older people. As for finding idioms and the connotation means that Chinese people often do not say anything directly, both in speaking and in writing, In order to maintain kindness and show one's own level of knowledge.

Keywords: Cultural Vocabulary, Chinese Novel, “Three Lives Three Worlds Ten Miles of Peach Blossoms”

Introduction

Chinese novels were translated to Thai have started since the beginning of Rattanakosin period in 1782. King Rama I translated 2 Chinese Books of Chronicles to Thai. They were Sai Han and Romance of Three Kingdoms. The important translation target was to give the knowledge about the warfare strategies or the art of war. Besides, it was found that some Chinese literatures translated at the end of this period were liked novels about internal power, but Thai people didn't know the word "Novels about internal power" yet. They also understood that those composed stories were about Chronicles. In 1963, there were amusing Chinese novels about internal power, there was also Chin Bumroongphong's translation style which was tight and precise. His pen name was Wor Na Mueang Loong. This person made Chinese novels about internal power to be popular again.

Before 2008, the printing press produced novels in the Sweet Asian style and in the Jamsai Love Series style which were new-style love novels, such as love of teenagers from Taiwan, Japan, and Korea. Later, it wanted to produce novels in other styles. It produced novels in the fantasy style like Dreamland of Love. The story which was well accepted by readers was "The Flame's Daughter". It is the novel from Taiwan. Its content was the historical period style mixed with internal power. So, the printing press produced more works in the historical period style, and Thai reader women liked Chinese novels in the historical period style more than before. (Kulsiri Angsanunsook and Kanokporn Noomthong, 2018)

For the story "Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms", it was the ancient Chinese novel about Chinese Gods. It was written by TangQiGongZi. It is about the love and the malice during three worlds between Fox God with nine tails, Bai Qian, and the prince who was the heir of heaven Ye Hua Tribe. It was very famous novel in China and taken to make the script for the television drama. After it was broadcasted as the first Chinese series, there were 40,000 millions audiences. In 2017, its copyright was bought and broadcasted in Thailand. In 2009, Suree Pruksanusuck, the owner of Sureeporn Printing Press, decided to buy the copyright from the writer, TangQiGongZi.

The narration of this book was complex, and the writing style was graceful. Expressions, connotation, pronouns, poems, jokes of Chinese people, belief, and any legends of Chinese Gods were in all of the story. There also were positions and many practices for the promotion of Chinese Gods inserted in the story, for example, "Shang Shen" was the highest level of Chinese Gods, the lower was Shang Xian and Xian (the normal level). Chinese Gods could be promoted if they passed the heaven checkpoint for two times. If they could pass, they would be promoted to be Shang Shen. They would have the lifetime as the sky existence. If they couldn't pass, they must die. (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012). They might pass the love destiny checkpoint. They must fight against obstacles, disappointment, or suffering because of love. When the writer and the translator were in the different societies, the translation this novel for Thai living in the Thai social context was difficult to understand. We could say that this book in the Thai version was hard to understand for people who began to read Chinese novels in the Thai version.

However, the researcher believed that reading this Chinese novel in the Thai version was the new method

and the starting point which we could learn the cultural of China because the language was the tool reflecting ideas, feeling, and attitudes. The language had the closed relation with the culture. When we studied and considered the method to translate words in many categories, we could understand that translators didn't translate the language only, they also translated ideas, feeling, and attitudes of Chinese people inevitably. If there were many different ideas, feeling, and attitudes, translators must use more technics. Peter Newmark had already sorted the types of cultural words so that translators could use them as the models when they found problems when they translated. They were environmental culture, objects culture, social culture, language cultural, and gestures and habits cultural (Supanee Pinmanee, 2019). Therefore, the researcher was interested in applying the theory of cultural words of Newmark for studying the novel "Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms" so that he could understand the target of writing this novel and the Chinese culture.

Objectives

1. Which cultural vocabulary meanings did the translator choose in the translation from Chinese to Thai in the novel "Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms"?
2. Which methods did the translator choose the most and the least for cultural vocabulary translation from Chinese to Thai in the novel "Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms"? And study meanings of cultural vocabularies which were categorized.

Scope

To study and compare this novel only "Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms" in the Chinese version of TangQiGongZi and the Thai version of Suree Pruksanusuck. There were 23 parts and 5 special parts.

Materials and methods

1. Research Instruments

The language and culture theories of Peter Newmark were used. Newmark (Newmark, 1998) sorted words relating the language and culture into 5 categories as follows:

1.1 Environmental Culture has specific meanings because the difference of locations or landscapes affected to weather, plants, or animals in those areas. That's why people used words for calling those creatures differently in each country.

1.2 Objects Culture was consisted of costumes, food, houses, appliances, and vehicles, etc., for example, Cheongsam or Hanfu of China, and Thai Jitlada Dress. When these costumes were used as the examples, they made us to think of China and Thailand.

1.3 Social Culture related with ideas, belief, or procedures which were hold in the society since the

ancient time, such as religions, stories, legends, and specific names of organizations, etc.

1.4 Language Cultural was the difference of language usage which was the identity of each area. Those appearances could be seen from expression usage, meanings of words, or relations of talkers through pronouns, such as words presenting people classes or relations.

1.5 Gestures and Habits Cultural was some manners which had specific meanings along customs and cultures of each nation. Sometimes, the same manners had different meanings, such as for the greeting, Thai people liked to pay respect while westerners liked to shake hands, etc

2. Data Collection

2.1 Collect cultural vocabularies from the novel “Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms” in the Chinese version written by TangQiGongZi and in the Thai version translated by Suree Pruksanusuck.

2.2 Finding meanings of cultural vocabularies from the original in the Chinese version and compare with meanings in the Thai version.

2.3 Collect data having Chinese language cultural in the original and meanings comparing with the Thai version. Then, put the data in the table for analyzing later.

3. Data Analysis

3.1 Study and analyze cultural vocabulary from the novel “Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms” as the measures of analysis the theory of Newmark. There were 5 methods : Environmental Culture, Objects Culture, Social Culture, Language Cultural, and Gestures and Habits Culture.

3.2 Present the result of analysis of cultural vocabulary from Chinese to Thai in the form of table presenting numbers and the result in percentage.

3.3 Conclude the result of analysis the cultural vocabulary translation which the translator choose to use. There were the numbers of vocabularies used in the translation. They were sorted from being used the most to the least. The result was shown in the percentage.

Results

Part 1 Cultural vocabularies which the translator used in the translation from Chinese to Thai in the novel “Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms”

From comparing cultural vocabularies from the novel “Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms” in the Chinese version written by TangQiGongZi and in the Thai version written by Suree Pruksanusuck, there were 298 cultural vocabularies as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 showed 5 categories of Cultural Words and Percentage.

Environmental Culture	Number (words)	Percent
Environmental Culture	24	8.05
Objects Culture	39	13.09
Social Culture	103	34.56
. Language Culture	128	42.96
Gestures and Habits Culture	4	1.35
Total	298	100

From Table 1, cultural vocabularies which the translator chose to use had 5 methods : Environment Culture, Objects Culture, Social Culture, Language Cultural, and Gestures and Habits Cultural. The sample of language Cultural translation from Chinese to Thai in the novel “Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms” as follows:

1. Environmental Culture

Example Original: 她昏倒在东海之东折颜上神的十里桃花林里，折颜将她救醒后大是感叹。(TangQi, 2017, p. 9)

Translation: I lost consciousness in the east of Burapa Sea... in ten miles of **peach** forest of Zhe Yan Shangshen. He helped me until I regained consciousness and sighed deeply. (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012, p. 21)

“桃” (tao) meant peach trees, one kind of perennial plants, having many breeds, little branches, round and oval leaves, pink flowers, sweet fruits (Thienchai Eiamworamet, 2015, p. 1346) The translator didn't translate as Standard Chinese which pronounced “Tao” but pronounced as Chaozhou “Thor”.

2. Objects Culture

Example Original: 她习惯性地想要去揉眼睛，碰到缚眼的白绫时才想起来，眼睛已经没有了。(TangQi, 2017, p. 1)

Translation: I raised hands up and would rub eyes because of my habitude. When I touch white **satin cloth** binding, I could remember that there weren't eyes any longer (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012, p. 10)

“绫” (ling) meant satin cloth (Thienchai Eiamworamet, 2015, p. 856) The researcher thought that it came from slightly distorting of another Chinese vocabulary which was “缎” (duan) meant satin cloth (Thienchai Eiamworamet, 2015, p. 239) because both words had the same meaning. But Thais call this cloth type that “duan”, so the translator chose translate in Thai that “Duan Cloth”.

3. Social Culture

Example Original: 素素，因果轮回，欠了别人的债，是一定要还的。(TangQi, 2017, p. 5)

Translation: SuSu **the rule that you get what you deserve debts** that you owed others, you must compensate to them. (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012, p. 15)

“因果” (yinguo) meant anyone made badness, he must deserve it. (Thienchai Eiamworamet, 2015, p. 1767), “轮回” (lunhui) meant the cycle of birth and death in Buddhism (Thienchai Eiamworamet, 2015, p. 887). The translator translated these two words that “you get what you deserve” because they had the closet meaning, and Thai readers could understand more than the translation each word. The belief about retribution was in the vocabulary that Thais could understand because they believed in this thing like Chinese people.

4. Language Cultural

Example Original: 方才夜华形色匆匆，淡薄之间隐含亲切，梳理之间又暗藏婉约，如此神态，以本上神十多万年前所见的风明经验，定是会佳人去了。(TangQi, 2017, p. 32)

Translation: Recently, Ye Hua seemed in a hurry; in his cold manner, there was friendliness hidden; in his estrangement, there was the pity hidden. The facial expression and manner like this, from my experience of the Wind and Moon Story for a hundred thousand years, he surely must meet **his love**. (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012, p. 73)

“风明” (fengming) was shortened from “风明雪花” (fengmingxuehua) was the Chinese expression meant pieces or poems which were windy (Thienchai Eiamworamet, 2015, p. 386) Besides, it could mean the love story (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012, p. 300). Here, the translator translated the Wind and Moon Story “风” was the windy, and “明” was the moon. They were translated directly, but there was the hidden meaning of the love story.

5. Gestures and Habits Cultural

Example Original: 东海之外，大荒之中，是为青丘。说到这里，特特揖起双手向正东方的青丘拜了拜。(TangQi, 2017, p. 10)

Translation: Outside of Burapa Sea, In the center of mainland was QingQiu. Here, conjurers from south stars **raised their joined hands and respected** in the south direction where QingQiu was located intentionally (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012, p. 23)

“揖”(yi) in the written language was “揖让” (yirang) meant bending and joining hands for respect. This manner was made by guests and hosts when they met in the ancient time (Thienchai Eiamworamet, 2015, p. 1658). Bowing and respect were the manner of Chinese to greet when they met. In Thailand, it is not a new gesture. Because Thailand has many Thai people of Chinese descent and there is also a trend of globalization from read works of Chinese writers or watched Chinese films that makes the new generation of Thais know more about Chinese culture. so Thais could understand this manner well.

Part 2 Translation cultural vocabularies which the translator used the most and the least for the translation from Chinese to Thai in the novel “Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms”

From comparing cultural vocabularies from the novel “Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms” in Chinese and Thai versions, it found that there were 298 cultural vocabularies. They could be sorted into 5 categories : Language Cultural was found the most, next were Social Culture, Objects Culture,

Environmental Culture, and Gestures and Habits Cultural. So, if cultural vocabularies were sorted along the numbers and the percentage, the result would be as Table 2.

Table 2 showed the numbers, the percentage, and the times to be found from the most to the least of 5 categories of cultural vocabularies.

Environmental Culture	Number (words)	Percent	Rank
Environmental Culture	24	8.05	4
Objects Culture	39	13.09	3
Social Culture	103	34.56	2
. Language Culture	128	42.96	1
Gestures and Habits Culture	4	1.35	5
Total	298	100	

From the table, 5 categories of cultural words were found. Each category had the following details.

1. Environmental Culture, There were 24 words which could be sorted in 4 categories : 18 plant names, 4 fruit names, 1 animal name, and 1 place name, such as Pipa (loquat) or Thais called “Pee-Pae” because its shape seemed the Chinese musical instrument, Pipa. So, it was called in the same name. Pee-Pae was sweet but not much. It could relieve the cough. In Thailand, there were the cough syrup Shuan Pauy Pee Pae Kor and Shuan Pauy Pee Pae Lowh which Thais knew well although they never saw fruits.

2. Objects Culture ,There were 39 words which could be sorted in 3 categories : 20 appliance names, 16 construction material name, and 3 food name, such as PaiLou (ceremonial gateway) which was the arch. It was one of architectures of China in the ancient time. It was made from wood, stones, and bricks. It was built in gardens, temples, palaces, cemeteries, crossroads, and roads. In Thailand, PaiLou was seen at doors or entrances of Chinese temples.

3. Social Culture, There were 101 words which were sorted as follows:

3.1 Social Culture which related with 5 categories of belief and legends: There were 22 legend God names, 17 legend animal names, 32 place names, 7 magic weapon names, and 17 words about Buddhism-Zen belief, such as heaven with 9 floors. It was Chinese’ belief that the sky had 9 floors. On the 9th floor, Ling Xiao Pao Palace of The Jade Emperor was located. Lingpao Tianzun was one of 3 God masters of Zen. The 2 others were Yuanshi Tianzun and Daode Tianzun. Lingpao Tianzun was the god of intellect and academic matter. He helped people so that they could receive things that they hoped.

3.2 Social Culture which related with 6 categories of Chinese culture : 2 game words, 1 letter words, 2 festival words, 1 play, 1 philosophy word, and 1 fortune prediction word, such as Zhongyuan Festival. It was the festival name of Zen. Thais called “Ghost Festival”. It was a Full-moon day on the seventh lunar month of China. Di Guan or God of Soil taking care of the hell would release all ghosts and opened the hell door. Sacrificial offerings were put so that spirits of ancestors could go their homes. Incenses were lighted for

praying spirits of ancestors so that they would go to the heaven, and spirits who died in wars and strayed could be helped. Another important thing in Ghost Festival was the burning papers so that dead ancestors would receive money. A few papers must be burnt around crossroads so that straying spirits would receive money, and they didn't ask for some money from ancestors. In Thailand, Thais of Chinese descents set meat dishes like pork, duck, chicken, and dessert dishes like fruits and sweets for making offerings or sacrifice to spirits. Besides, some families burnt silver and gold papers while they made offerings. (Krukay Chinese, 2017)

4. Language Cultural, There were 128 words :

4.1 Language Cultural related with 2 types of pronouns.

4.1.1 17 pronouns for calling relatives, such as A Die using to call fathers in the ancient time, A Niang using to call mothers in the ancient time, ShuShu meant uncles, and GuGu meant aunts.

4.1.2 Language Cultural could be sorted to 2 categories : 17 pronouns for calling oneself, such as BenJun meant I who was God or King of Devil, XiaoShen meant I who was inferior God, NuBi meant I who was a maid; and 20 pronouns for calling others, such as NiangNiang using to call Queen, king's first concubine, or king's wives, JunShang was used by inferior Gods for calling superior Gods, Lao Ren Jia, meant old people, being used for calling respected adults like fathers, mothers, relatives, and teachers. (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012, p. 334-335)

4.2 Language Cultural related with positions in palaces there were 17 words, such as Tianjun was heaven rulers, Tianhou was Tianjun's wives, Taizi was heirs, and Taizi Fei was heirs' first wives.

4.3 Language Cultural related with 28 expressions, such as White cloud grey dog meant stories in the world could change and be never sure like white clouds could change their shapes in grey clouds (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012, p. 294), Flowers falling in love while rivers not love meant heart of flowers was left into flowing rivers, but rivers were on bad terms and uninterested in flowers (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012, p. 300), 29 words with hidden meanings, such as the color of peach blossom meant having the love fortune (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012, p. 21), or cut sleeves meant homosexuality between gays. (Suree Pruksanusuck, 2012, p. 298)

5. Gestures and Habits Culture There were 4 words as follows.

5.1 Salutation or respect presented the regard. Noblemen had an audience with royalty to the king. Soldiers in armies paid respect to army leaders. People who had inferior seniority or positions paid respect ones who had superior seniority or positions.

5.2 Kneeling Chinese people said "Men's knees were precious like gold. So, Chinese people easily kneeled because kneeling was used for punishment, paying respect or showing admire to people in higher ranks like parents or teachers.

5.3 Punishment with drinking 1 tumbler of liquor as the context in the novel because it was misunderstanding a bit. Players in the novel punished themselves by drinking liquor. They only relieved the shame. Those mistakes weren't serious.

5.4 Kneeling 3 times and Bowing 9 times were the Chinese prostrate. It was used for having an audience

with royalty or worship Gods. They must kneel and prostrate, and their heads reached to floors; then they stood upright. They must do these 3 times.

Conclusion

1. Studying cultural words from the novel “Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms” which was the novel about ancient Chinese Gods. It was written by TangQiGongzi, a modern writer. The target was to categorize cultural words and analyze those vocabularies. The research result was concluded that there was 5 categories of cultural words found in the novel : Environmental Culture, Objects Culture, Social Culture, Language Cultural, Gestures and Habits Cultural.

2. Cultural vocabularies which were found the most were 128 words of Language Cultural, for 42.96%, Next were 103 words of Social Culture, for 34.56%, 39 words of Objects Culture, for 13.09%, 24 words of Environmental Culture, for 8.05%, and 4 words of Gestures and Habits Cultural, for 1.35%. The cultural words which were found the most was Language Cultural, next were Social Culture, Objects Culture, Environmental Culture, and Gestures and Habits Cultural. Found language cultural was pronoun usage for calling relatives, oneself, others, and names of many positions. It showed that the Chinese society held the seniority system, the class division, the respect and modesty to old people or anyone who had in higher ranks. It was found in the ancient time and inherited until present. It was similar to the Thai society. If the present Chinese society wasn't like this, both Chinses and Thai readers couldn't understand contexts of players, and this novel couldn't be famous in China and Thailand. Besides, the usage expressions and meanings hidden in the story showed that Chinese never showed directly. They always used expressions and metaphors which appeared in both writing and conversation works for showing the good manners, keeping the goodwill, and the education levels.

Discussion

Cultural vocabularies from studying the novel “Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms” were 5 categories of cultural words : Environmental Culture, Objects Culture, Social Culture, Language Cultural, and Gestures and Habits Cultural. Language Cultural was found the most, Cultural vocabularies which were found the most was Language Cultural which was the usage pronouns for calling relatives, oneself, or others. Gestures and Habits Cultural was found at least. It conformed to the result of the research about strategies used of translating cultural terms found in the English version of the Thai novel “The teachers of mad dog swamp” of Athisa Ngarnsri (2017) which Language Cultural was found the most, Language Cultural was found the most because there were words presenting the class ranks appearing in the conversation all of the story. This story was during villagers, teachers, government officers. Gestures and Habits Cultural was found the least.

There were 6 categories of cultural words which didn't relate to the research : Environmental Culture, Objects Culture, Social Culture, Language Cultural, and Gestures and Habits Cultural. Besides, cultural

words which were found didn't sort as same. In Athisa Ngarnsri's research, they were sorted as follows : Language Cultural was found the most, next were Objects Culture, Environmental Culture, Social Culture, and Gestures and Habits Cultural.

Suggestions

1. This research emphasized sorting categories of cultural words from the novel "Three lives three worlds, Ten miles of peach blossoms" ; then, those Chinese vocabularies were taken to analyze for studying the Chinese culture only, but in the theories and strategies to translate cultural vocabularies, there were 3 sides which could proceed to study : the side of words, texts, and meanings, the side of grammar and structure, and the side of language usage, talking methods, words choosing in suitable levels and styles.
2. The researcher had the time limit, so we could study only one Chinese novel. Any researchers who continued the research next time could study many Chinese novels in the same time, compared the Chinese culture during each period, and studied how each period could affect ideas or belief of Thais. Besides, if researchers had the proficiency in other languages, they could use novels from USA, England, France, German, Japan, or Korea for comparing in several points of view.

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